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Effects of noise on pedestrians in urban environments where road traffic is the main source of sound --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Research combining the measurement of objective variables with surveys of people's perception of noise on city streets is useful in terms of understanding the impact of urban noise on the population and improving the environment. Although previous investigations have analysed the factors that may influence the noise annoyance of citizens, it is usually considered as a global aspect. This paper presents research based on in situ surveys and objective variables (urban, meteorological and noise indicators) to evaluate some specific effects of noise on pedestrians in urban environments where road traffic is the main source of sound. The results show significant relationships of the effects of noise and perceptions of how noisy urban environments are with variables such as building height, road category and temperature, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.37 to 0.64. Significant correlations between these subjective variables and the acoustic variables were also found, with explanations of variability that reached values of up to 50%. A multivariate analysis revealed that both urban variables (especially the category of street) and environmental variables can be an alternative or a complement to models predicting the effects and perception of environmental noise based only on acoustic variables.</p>
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Reviewers/Editor comments:</p> <p>Reviewer #1: Comment No. 1: After the authors have made corrections and additions, the quality of the article is much better and in my opinion it is suitable for publication. Response to Reviewer #1 comment No. 1: The authors would like to thank the reviewer for the comment.</p> <p>Reviewer #2: Comment No. 1: Authors' response regarding only 105 (sample size) responses/people surveyed does not seem feasible to me. This is very small sample size for a study having 29 locations. It means that only 3 to 4 people/respondents participated in the survey at each selected location. How representative of such a small sample can represent the opinion/view of the major/entire population of a city? Authors must state clearly that how many people were surveyed at each selected location? Response to Reviewer #2 comment No. 1: The authors understand the reviewer's concern about the representativeness of a sample of 105 individuals. For this reason, the authors showed in the previous version of the article that the tests they are using (bivariate correlations and multiple regressions) are sufficiently powerful for a sample of 105 individuals. Also, they showed that taking into account the population of Cáceres (96,000 inhabitants approximately) and the variability recorded in previous studies, the error is 0.5 (lines 143-148 in the new version of the manuscript). Indeed, when this study was planned, the aim was to conduct more than 105 surveys. But the declaration of a state of alert due to COVID-19 stopped the study for about 2 years and</p>

Highlights

- Increase in some noise effects perceived by pedestrians with building height
- Significant negative correlation between temperature and some noise effects
- Good explanations of the variability of noise effects from some acoustic variables
- Urban-environmental models to significantly explain the perception of noise effects
- Categorisation method could help to predict noise effects on pedestrians in cities

24 and environmental variables can be an alternative or a complement to models predicting
25 the effects and perception of environmental noise based only on acoustic variables.

26 **Keywords:** effects of noise, noise annoyance, road traffic noise, *in situ* survey, urban
27 variables, environmental variables.

28 **1. INTRODUCTION**

29 Environmental noise pollution in urban contexts is one of the challenges facing society
30 today, mainly due to its impact on human health and well-being (EEA, 2020).

31 Infrastructures for the transport of people and goods are considered to be the main source
32 of noise in this type of environment. In fact, transport noise has become the second most
33 important environmental source of ill health in Europe, after fine particulate matter
34 pollution (WHO, 2018). Recent research keeps pointing out a close relationship between
35 traffic noise and different types of diseases and health disorders such as anxiety (Lan et
36 al., 2020) (Hegewald et al., 2020), depression and psychological problems (Eze et al.,
37 2020) (Baudin et al., 2018), obesity (Cai et al., 2020) (Foraster et al., 2018), hypertension
38 and cardiovascular risk (Baudin et al., 2020) (Khosravipour and Khanlari, 2020),
39 annoyance and sleep disorders (Paiva et al., 2019) (Basner and McGuire, 2018), and
40 metabolic diseases (Huang et al., 2020) (Thiesse et al., 2018). Traffic noise is not an
41 isolated issue, and is associated with other aspects such as urban planning (Renterghem
42 et al., 2020) (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021b) (Yuan et al., 2019), air quality (Silva and
43 Mendes, 2012), socio-economic factors (Xu et al., 2020) (Tong and Kang, 2021) and
44 weather conditions (Guan et al., 2020) (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021).

45 The study of environmental noise levels in cities using the noise indicators for day (L_d),
46 evening (L_e), night (L_n) and day-evening-night (L_{den}) established in the European Noise
47 Directive (END, 2002) is often carried out by means of strategic noise maps considering

48 the different sources of noise (Ozkurt et al., 2014) (Paschalidou et al., 2019) (Hinze et al.,
49 2022) and following the guidelines of international guidelines and standards (WG-AEN,
50 2007) (ISO 1996-2, 2017). In the specific case of road traffic noise, which is considered
51 to be the main source of environmental noise (EEA, 2014), simulations using commercial
52 software are carried out for this purpose taking into account different variables such as
53 vehicle flow (Ascari et al., 2015) (Fiedler and Zannin, 2015), sound power (Barrigón
54 Morillas et al., 2021), vehicle speed (Ögren et al., 2018), and the characteristics of the
55 façades (Calleri et al., 2018). These noise models are validated through long- and short-
56 term *in situ* measurements (Zagubieñ and Wolniewicz, 2021) (Montes González et al.,
57 2020a) (Aletta et al., 2020) that follow different sampling strategies (Quintero et al., 2019)
58 (Gómez Escobar et al., 2012a) and measurement procedures (Montes González et al.,
59 2020b) (ANSI S12.18, 1994). Based on the results of noise maps for the exposure of the
60 population to noise pollution, action plans for the mitigation of environmental noise are
61 then designed (Ögren et al., 2018) (Vázquez et al., 2016). In addition, initiatives related
62 to urban planning that focus on the development and promotion of quiet areas have been
63 proposed in the scientific literature to try to make these types of environments more
64 pleasant for the resident population and to improve the sense of well-being (Calleja et al.,
65 2017) (Rey Gozalo et al., 2019) (Vogiatzis and Remy, 2017) (Hong et al., 2020).

66 However, there is a growing tendency to complement this type of research based on
67 objective noise indices with studies that allow us to obtain an assessment of people's
68 satisfaction with the sound quality of urban spaces (Koprowska et al., 2018) (Youssoufi
69 et al., 2020) (Aletta et al., 2018). The concept of sound quality can be understood as the
70 degree of adequacy of the acoustic characteristics of a space to the activities carried out
71 in the area. In this regard, conducting surveys on city streets is an approach that provides
72 interesting information for an analysis of the degree of satisfaction and annoyance of

73 residents, not only in relation to the sound environment but also to other features such as
74 cleanliness, air quality, aesthetics of the environment, odours, etc. (Lionello et al., 2020)
75 (Engel et al., 2020) (Jiang et al., 2016) (Ba and Kang, 2019).

76 Noise indicators such as L_{Aeq} , L_{AFmin} , L_{AFmax} y L_N are commonly used in environmental
77 noise studies (Paszkowski et al., 2018) (Maristany et al., 2016). The effects of noise are
78 generally measured based on indicators that take the equivalent A-weighted sound level
79 as a reference (WHO, 2011) (ISO 1996-2, 2017) (END, 2002), although the maximum
80 sound level is also considered in this regard (WHO, 2018). The relationships between
81 objective acoustic indices and subjective variables related to the effects of noise in cities
82 can be studied in order to analyse which aspects can influence annoyance of citizens and
83 their preferences for the use of urban spaces (Bouزيد et al., 2020) (Van Gerven et al.,
84 2009) (Estévez-Mauriz et al., 2018) (Ma et al., 2021), so that these can be taken into
85 consideration by urban planners at the design stage. Most previous research has only
86 assessed the overall effect of noise in terms of annoyance, but a consideration of more
87 specific aspects of the effects of noise on people may also be of interest. In addition, it is
88 also interesting to analyse the influence of environmental and urban variables on the
89 perception or effects of noise in the same way as was done with physical characteristics
90 of sound and people-related factors (Ouis, 2001).

91 This paper presents the results of research carried out by means of *in situ* surveys and
92 measurements in Cáceres (Spain) to assess the effects of noise on people in urban
93 environments in which road traffic is the main sound source and to study its relationships
94 with urban, environmental and acoustic variables.

95 **2. METHODOLOGY**

96 **2.1 Survey, sampling and data collection procedure**

97 The methodology followed in this study was based on a process of *in situ* surveys and
98 measurements, carried out simultaneously by four people in the streets of Cáceres (Spain),
99 in which values of both subjective and objective variables were collected. This study was
100 carried out on working days (Monday to Friday) in the time period from 9 a.m. to 7 p.m,
101 during the year 2020 (January and February) before the COVID-19 alarm state. The
102 sampling points were randomly selected on urban roads with different functionality for
103 vehicle mobility. Thus, they were sampled from main city streets, Category 1, used for
104 connection to other cities or interconnection of preferred streets, to Category 5 streets
105 corresponding to residential neighbourhood streets (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021). The
106 objective was to sample different urban settings with variability in urban and
107 environmental characteristics. For this purpose, 29 different locations were sampled in
108 the city of Cáceres as shown in Figure 1.

109

110 Figure 1. Locations of the surveys and measuring points in Cáceres (from Google Earth)

111 The design of the survey was approved by the ethics and bioethics committee of the
112 University of Extremadura (37//2020), and an informed consent form was filled out by
113 each participant in each survey, according to the Declaration of Helsinki. The effects of
114 environmental noise on people walking down the street was the dimension assessed in
115 the survey using nine questions. An 11-point numerical scale was used for each question
116 (where 0 was “not at all” and 10 “extremely”). The points on this numerical scale are
117 equally spaced and therefore provides a justification for treating the data as continuous in
118 statistical tests (ISO/TS 15666, 2021). This type of scale is more suitable for linear
119 regression analysis (Brink et al., 2016). The 11-point numerical scale is recommended by
120 the International Standardisation Organisation (ISO/TS 15666, 2021) and used in current
121 studies (Brink et al., 2019) (Schäffer et al., 2020) because it also has advantages over

122 verbal scales in its comprehension by people of different nationalities (Fields et al., 2001).
123 Face-to-face was the method used for data collection in the survey. Any evidence of
124 hearing loss detected by the interviewer during the presentation or conduct of the survey
125 led to the exclusion of the responses obtained. In the first seven questions related to effect
126 of noise (see Table 1), respondents were asked to what extent or how often the
127 environmental noise in that street causes them: a) irritability; b) startle; c) annoyance in
128 the ears; d) interrupting a conversation with someone nearby; e) raising the volume of
129 their voice to speak with someone nearby; f) interrupting a phone conversation; and g)
130 raising the volume of their voice on a phone conversation. Respondents were also asked
131 to rate their perceptions of the environment was h) in the city in general; and i) on that
132 particular street. Other demographic characteristics were also collected: age, sex and level
133 of education.

134 Different aspects have been considered to justify the representativeness of the sample
135 size. Fritz and Mackinnon (Fritz and MacKinnon, 2007) point out the importance of
136 having sample sizes necessary for 0.8 power for the tests to be used. Therefore, the
137 appropriate sample size for correlation and multiple linear regression was determined
138 using G*Power software (Kang, 2021). It was deduced that 100 people were required for
139 a power of 0.95 and a medium effect size according to Cohen (Cohen, 1988). On the other
140 hand, Nunnally (Nunnally, 1978) and Thorndike (Thorndike, 1982) recommend a sample
141 size 10 times the number of items. The present study had 9 items; therefore, the
142 recommended sample would be 90 subjects. However, Kline (Kline, 1994) suggests
143 sampling at least 100 subjects when the number of items is low. Finally, taking into
144 account the number of inhabitants of the city of Cáceres and the variability in the scores
145 registered in preliminary studies ($\sigma \approx 2.8$), the estimate of the population mean for a
146 sample size of 105 subjects would give an error of 0.5 (Rodríguez del Águila and

147 González-Ramírez, 2014). This error is not high and is similar to the standard error of the
 148 mean that would be obtained in the study. A total of 105 people were surveyed (44% of
 149 whom were male and 56% female, aged between 17 and 80, with education from primary
 150 to university level) despite the low response rate (25%) and the termination of the study
 151 due to COVID's state alarm. A similar number of surveys were completed at each
 152 sampling point.

153 It is not unusual to find previous studies with a sample size similar to this study. Fritz and
 154 Mackinnon (Fritz and MacKinnon, 2007) show results from a review of the survey
 155 literature where more than 50% of the studies have a sample size of less than 200. Douglas
 156 (Douglas and Murphy, 2016), Van Renterghem (Van Renterghem and Botteldooren,
 157 2012), Pirrera (Pirrera et al., 2014), Tao (Tao et al., 2020) and Paiva (Paiva et al., 2019)
 158 carried out survey studies in highly populated urban areas with a similar number of
 159 surveys to show the representativeness of the overall perception in the city where each
 160 survey was conducted at a different point/household.

161 Table 1. Subjective and objective variables registered in the city of Cáceres

Variables		Meaning	Value range
Subjective variables (survey)	a)	Irritability	0 – 10
	b)	Startle	0 – 10
	c)	Annoyance ears	0 – 10
	d)	Interrupting conversation	0 – 10
	e)	Raising volume	0 – 10
	f)	Interrupting phone	0 – 10
	g)	Raising phone	0 – 10
	h)	Noisy city	0 – 10
	i)	Noisy street	0 – 10
Objective variables Urban	L	Street length	85 – 1000 m
	W	Street width	9 – 40 m
	H	Average buildings height	0 – 27 m

	H/W	Relationship between building height and street width	0 – 1.6
	SC	Street category	1 – 5
	T	Temperature	9 – 23 °C
	RH	Relative humidity	19 – 95 %
Environ.	AP	Air pressure	1000 – 1013 hPa
	WS	Wind speed	0 – 3.5 m/s
	LU	Luminosity	1 – 94 klux
	<i>L_{Aeq}</i>	A-weighted equivalent sound level	48 – 73 dB
	<i>L_{AFmax}</i>	A-weighted maximum sound level	70 – 89 dB
Acoustic	<i>L_{AF10}</i>	A-weighted 10th percentile sound level	47 – 77 dB
	<i>L_{AF50}</i>	A-weighted 50th percentile sound level	40 – 70 dB
	<i>L_{AF90}</i>	A-weighted 90th percentile sound level	37 – 60 dB

162

163 The objective variables were classified into three different groups (see Table 1) and were
 164 collected both through a GIS database of Cáceres and with visual inspection on site
 165 simultaneously with the surveys. First, a set of urban variables associated with the features
 166 of the street were registered, such as the length (L) and width (W) of the street, the average
 167 height of the buildings (H), the relationship between building height and street width
 168 (H/W), and the category of street (SC). The streets were classified into the following
 169 categories (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021):

- 170 • Category 1: Preferential streets for connection with other towns and
 171 interconnection of those preferential streets.
- 172 • Category 2: Streets that provide access to major distribution nodes in a town or
 173 are used as an alternative to category 1 during traffic saturation.
- 174 • Category 3: Streets that lead to regional roads, streets that provide access from
 175 street categories 1 and 2 to centres of interest in a town (hospitals, shopping malls,
 176 etc.), and streets that clearly allow communication between street categories 1 and
 177 2.

- 178 • Category 4: All of the other streets that clearly allow communication between the
179 three previously defined types and the principal streets in a town's different
180 districts that were not included in the previously defined categories.
- 181 • Category 5: The rest of a town's streets except traffic-restricted streets.

182 Next, a group of variables related to environmental conditions were registered. The
183 temperature (T), relative humidity (RH) and air pressure (AP) were measured at
184 microphone height by a portable weather station, and monitoring was carried out to ensure
185 that the wind speed (WS) did not exceed 5 m/s. The luminosity (LU) at each measuring
186 point was also logged using a luxmeter. Considering that indicated in the Weber-Fechner
187 Law (Dehaene, 2003) (Reichl et al., 2010), the logarithm of luminosity (logLU) was
188 considered to study its relationship with the effects of noise.

189 Finally, different sound indicators were measured using a type 1 analyser, including the
190 A-weighted equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}), the maximum sound level (L_{AFmax}) and the
191 percentile levels (L_{10} , L_{50} and L_{90}). For this purpose, a type 1 sound level meter-analyser
192 was used, and the microphone was placed 1.5 m above the ground and at a similar distance
193 (2 m from the nearest point of the sound source) from the main sound source of road
194 traffic (Montes González et al., 2020b). Fifteen minutes sound measurements were made
195 avoiding placing the microphone on reflective surfaces (Montes González et al., 2018).
196 If the microphone was placed at a distance between 0.5 and 2 m from the building façade,
197 a correction of -3 dB was applied following the recommendations of ISO 1996-2 (ISO
198 1996-2, 2017; Montes González et al., 2020a). A verification of the calibration before and
199 after each series of measurements was carried out using a type 1 sound calibrator. The
200 sound measurements were carried out simultaneously with the surveys as indicated above.
201 The researcher conducting the sound measurements was separated at a sufficient distance
202 so that the sound levels registered were not influenced by the interviewers. At least one

203 sound measurement was performed at each sampling point. In addition, sound sources
204 were registered during the measurements. Road traffic was the main noise source with a
205 significant presence at the different sampling points. In fact, total traffic flow explained
206 83% of the variability of L_{Aeq} (dB).

207 **2.2 Statistical analysis**

208 The average values of the objective and subjective variables registered in the
209 measurements performed at each sampling point (N=29) were used in the subsequent
210 descriptive and inferential analyses. The responses obtained at each sampling point were
211 averaged considering different aspects. The urban variables are static and the
212 environmental and noise variables presented a low variability at each sampling point (see
213 Figure 2 in the Supplementary Material). The responses given to each subjective variable
214 also presented a stable and low variability at each sampling point as shown in Figure 1 in
215 the Supplementary Material. Therefore, similar results are obtained in the per-survey and
216 per-point correlation analyses as shown in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. However, the analysis by
217 surveys does not meet the premises of normality, homoscedasticity and linearity (an
218 expected result given the no or low variability of the objective variables) leading to a loss
219 of test power (non-parametric tests have lower power) and the impossibility of performing
220 bivariate and multivariate linear regression analyses. Furthermore, considering the
221 difference in the number of respondents between the different points and the fact that the
222 variability of the variables is due to their different locations, a treatment by surveys would
223 bias the results towards those points with a greater number of surveys.

224 A descriptive analysis of the average values and their deviation was carried out with the
225 subjective variables, i.e., those related to the effects of noise. This descriptive analysis
226 was complemented by a comparative study of the mean values using the *t*-test. Parametric

227 tests were used since the variables met the assumptions of normality, homoscedasticity
228 and linearity. Next, an analysis of the relationships between the objective and subjective
229 variables was carried out. First, the significance of the relationship between the two types
230 of variables was analysed using Pearson's correlation coefficient, except for the "street
231 category" variable, where Spearman's correlation coefficient was used, given its ordinal
232 nature. Next, a bivariate regression analysis was carried out for those variables that
233 showed a significant correlation. Finally, only those variables that did not show
234 collinearity (variance inflation factor < 5) and which contributed to a significant increase
235 in the explanation of the subjective variables were included in the multivariate regression
236 models. Stepwise regression and the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) were used to
237 choose the best performing model.

238 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

239 This section presents an analysis of the results obtained for the effects of noise on people
240 and the relationships between the subjective and objective variables, and is organised into
241 subsections corresponding to the different groups defined for the objective variables.

242 **3.1. Noise and its effects**

243 As a starting point, Figure 2 shows the mean and the error in the mean for the responses
244 obtained in all the streets surveyed for questions a) to i) described in Section 2 in relation
245 to the effects of noise on people. Figure 2 reveals that the only noise effects with mean
246 values of above 3 were irritability (3.6) and startle (3.3). Around the mean value of 3 were
247 the effects of annoyance in the ears (2.9) and raising the volume in a conversation, either
248 with someone present in the environment (3.0) or talking on the telephone (2.8). Below
249 these values, around a mean value of 2.5, the effects of interrupting a conversation were
250 found, with a value of 2.6 when face-to-face and 2.5 on the phone. Although a statistical

251 analysis using *t*-test only showed the existence of significant differences ($p < 0.05$)
252 between the effect of irritability and the effects of interrupting a conversation face-to-face
253 or on the phone, the existence of a consistency can be considered in the mean results. It
254 can be observed for example that for both means of communication, the effect of raising
255 the volume of the voice reaches higher mean values than that of interrupting a
256 conversation.

257 When analysing the values for the participants' perceptions of how noisy is the city or
258 street in which the survey was conducted, it can be noted that the city was rated at a value
259 of 5.5, that is, above the average value of the employed scale. While the street was rated
260 at 4.8, very close to the average value of the scale. If comparing these results for the noise
261 perception of an environment with the values obtained for the specific effects of noise, it
262 can be found that there is a significant increase in the average values. In fact, a statistical
263 analysis using *t*-test revealed significant differences in both values of the perception with
264 respect to all the values of the effects. For "noisy city", a significant difference with $p <$
265 0.001 was found in all cases. While for "noisy street", a significant difference with $p <$
266 0.05 was obtained for irritability and startle and $p < 0.001$ for the others. No significant
267 differences were detected between "noisy city" and "noisy street".

268 Given that this study considered a number of specific noise effects, it was difficult to find
269 previous research in the scientific literature that treated these effects in the same way in
270 order to establish a direct comparison and discussion. In the particular case of annoyance,
271 some authors have reported ratings of the general perception of noise annoyance that
272 would somehow cover all the specific noise effects addressed in the present study
273 (Öhrström et al., 2006) (Gómez Escobar et al., 2012b). Taking this into account, it would
274 be expected that in general, the rating of overall perceived annoyance in similar urban
275 environments would be higher than for each of the effects analysed separately. Other

276 research also analysed the annoyance perceived by people in green areas and urban parks
 277 considering various types of sound sources, and distinctions have been drawn, for
 278 example, between annoyance caused by construction, screams, animals and road traffic
 279 (Rey Gozalo et al., 2019).

280

281 Figure 2. Mean and standard error of the ratings given for all the streets surveyed for the
 282 subjective variables related to effects of noise on people.

283 **3.2. Analysis of the relationships between subjective and objective variables**

284 The outcomes obtained from the analysis of the correlations between subjective and
 285 objective variables are shown in Table 2. With regard to the urban variables, only two of
 286 the variables considered in this group (average building height and street category)
 287 showed significant correlations with the subjective variables related to noise and its
 288 effects. The L, W, and H/W did not show any significant correlation with the subjective
 289 variables ($p > 0.05$). Both urban variables (H and SC) differ in the number of subjective
 290 variables with which they have significant relationships and in the intensity of these
 291 relationships. While the height variable is strictly geometric, the street category is based
 292 on the functionality of the street as a means of communication. According to the results

293 reported in previous studies, road categories significantly stratify noise, so that noise
 294 values decrease from Categories 1 to 5 (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021). The subjective
 295 variables analysed here with respect to the effects and perception of noise show a
 296 significant negative correlation with respect to the road category, except for items c) and
 297 h) . The degree of association between the type of road and the subjective variables related
 298 to raising the voice showed associations with a degree of significance of less than 0.001,
 299 which are comparable to those found for the noise indicators. Concerning the
 300 environmental variables, the temperature showed the greatest number of significant
 301 relationships with the answers given by the respondents. In addition, the variables of
 302 atmospheric pressure and luminosity showed only one significant relationship, in these
 303 cases with the perception of how noisy the environment was in the street and city,
 304 respectively. The RH and WS did not show any significant correlation with the subjective
 305 variables ($p > 0.05$). Finally, the acoustic variables generally showed significant negative
 306 relationships with all or almost all of the subjective variables studied with a greater or
 307 smaller degree of association. This indicates that, as expected, there is a close relationship
 308 between the sound indicators and the effects of noise. It can be noted that the L_{Aeq} , L_{AF10}
 309 and L_{AF50} indicators are associated with all the subjective variables analysed here; the
 310 L_{AF90} indicator is associated with almost all of them, while L_{AFMax} is the indicator that
 311 shows the weakest relationship with the subjective variables.

312 Table 2. Correlation coefficient between objective and subjective variables

		Subjective variables								
		a)	b)	c)	d)	e)	f)	g)	h)	i)
Urban variables	H (m)	0.37*	0.41*	0.44*	0.19 n.s.	0.08 n.s.	0.02 n.s.	0.02 n.s.	-0.13 n.s.	0.41*
	SC	-0.44**	-0.48**	-0.20 n.s.	-0.62***	-0.58***	-0.49**	-0.64***	-0.29 n.s.	-0.53**
Environ. variables	T (°C)	-0.41*	-0.39*	-0.32 n.s.	-0.43*	-0.48**	-0.18 n.s.	-0.32 n.s.	0.43*	-0.44*
	AP (hPa)	-0.30 n.s.	-0.23 n.s.	-0.26 n.s.	-0.11 n.s.	-0.24 n.s.	-0.13 n.s.	-0.22 n.s.	0.09 n.s.	-0.38*
	logLU	-0.21 n.s.	-0.32 n.s.	-0.22 n.s.	-0.06 n.s.	-0.32 n.s.	0.12 n.s.	-0.13 n.s.	0.52**	-0.29 n.s.

Acoustic variables	<i>L_{Aeq}</i> (dB)	0.69 ^{***}	0.61 ^{***}	0.46 [*]	0.63 ^{***}	0.65 ^{***}	0.54 ^{**}	0.64 ^{***}	-0.38 [*]	0.63 ^{***}
	<i>L_{AFmax}</i> (dB)	0.57 ^{**}	0.41 [*]	0.26 ^{n.s.}	0.44 [*]	0.50 ^{**}	0.28 ^{n.s.}	0.42 [*]	-0.50 ^{**}	0.47 [*]
	<i>L_{AF10}</i> (dB)	0.71 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.49 ^{**}	0.62 ^{***}	0.65 ^{***}	0.54 ^{**}	0.63 ^{***}	-0.38 [*]	0.64 ^{***}
	<i>L_{AF50}</i> (dB)	0.71 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.59 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.70 ^{***}	0.60 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	-0.38 [*]	0.66 ^{***}
	<i>L_{AF90}</i> (dB)	0.64 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.61 ^{***}	0.64 ^{***}	0.57 ^{**}	0.62 ^{***}	-0.30 ^{n.s.}	0.64 ^{***}

313 ^{n.s.} Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).

314 ^{*} Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

315 ^{**} Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

316 ^{***} Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

317 **3.2.1. Urban variables**

318 Table 3 shows the values of the different parameters of the regression analysis between
319 the subjective variables and the average building height (H) that showed a significant
320 correlation in Table 2. The values of this independent variable ranged between 0 and 27
321 m for the studied streets as shown in Table 1.

322 Table 3. Regression parameters among all subjective variables and the objective urban
323 variable of average building height (H)

		Subjective variables			
		a)	b)	c)	i)
Average building height (H)	Slope	0.11	0.11	0.13	0.11
	Intercept	1.83	1.55	0.92	3.09
	Determination coefficient	0.14 [*]	0.17 [*]	0.20 [*]	0.17 [*]

324 ^{*} Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

325 When the results obtained for average building height (H) are analysed, it is possible to
326 see that this variable can explain between 14% and 20% of the variation in the subjective
327 variables related to the effects of noise on the population in urban environments, such as
328 irritability (14%), startle (17%), annoyance in the ears (20%) and the perception of how
329 noisy the street is (17%). Considering results obtained in previous studies, the explanation
330 of the variability of subjective variables by the predictor H is not low. It should be noted

331 that these previous studies used multiple predictor variables and acoustic variables. This
332 study has the novelty of analysing the perception of specific noise effects and the specific
333 contribution of predictor variables based on urban and environmental features. Average
334 building height and other building characteristics are also used as independent variables
335 to predict noise annoyance in multivariate models. Although these models may have a
336 better explanation of the variability than the one obtained in this study, it must be
337 considered that they are models with many independent variables. Preisendörfer et al.
338 (Preisendörfer et al., 2022) obtain explanations of the variability for road traffic
339 annoyance between 23% and 31% using multivariate models that include 17 factors,
340 including some related to building characteristics. Another recent study obtained a
341 McFadden's pseudo r-squared value of 0.263 for the multivariate noise annoyance model
342 including seven independent variables (Chung et al., 2022).

343 Table 3 also shows that most the values of the slope coefficient for the four subjective
344 variables are similar and positive; that is, the noise effects related to these variables that
345 respondents report to perceive increase as the average height of the buildings increases.
346 When the average building height (H) rises from the minimum to the maximum values of
347 the range studied here (0–27 m), irritability (a) ranges between 1.8 and 4.8; startle (b)
348 increases from 1.6 to 4.5; annoyance in the ears (c) rises from 0.9 to 4.4; and the
349 perception of how noisy the street is i) increases from 3.1 to 6.1. Although the maximum
350 height of the streets under evaluation was 27 m, corresponding to buildings of
351 approximately nine storeys, there are large cities in which the height of buildings is
352 greater than this. It would therefore be interesting to continue this line of research by
353 expanding the study to cities containing streets with larger average building heights.

354 **3.2.2 Environmental variables**

355 The results of the regression analysis between the subjective variables and the
 356 environmental variables with significant correlations in Table 2 are shown in Table 4.
 357 The values of the slope, intercept coefficient, coefficient of determination (R^2) and
 358 significance level are given for the variable of temperature (T). Since in the case of air
 359 pressure (AP) and luminosity (logLU), a significant correlation was only found for one
 360 of the subjective variables, the results are shown in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 for air pressure (AP)
 361 and luminosity (logLU), respectively. The ranges of these independent variables were
 362 approximately 9–23 °C for temperature, 1000–1013 hPa for air pressure and 1–94 klux
 363 for luminosity as shown in Table 1.

364 Table 4. Regression parameters between the subjective variables and the environmental
 365 variable of temperature (T).

		Subjective variables					
		a)	b)	d)	e)	h)	i)
Temperature (T)	Slope	-0.22	-0.18	-0.22	-0.28	0.13	-0.21
	Intercept	6.83	5.93	5.78	7.05	3.6	7.94
	Determination coefficient	0.17*	0.15*	0.18*	0.23**	0.18*	0.20*

367 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

368 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

369

370
$$i = 211.82 - 0.21 \cdot AP \ (R^2 = 0.14) \quad \text{(Eq. 1)}$$

371
$$h = 44.31 + 1.58 \cdot \log LU \ (R^2 = 0.27) \quad \text{(Eq. 2)}$$

372 Among the environmental variables in Table 2, temperature (T) shows significant
 373 relationships with several subjective variables such as a), b), d), e), h) and, i). In this
 374 regard, temperature can explain between 15% and 23% of the variability of these

375 subjective variables. In contrast, the remaining two environmental variables only showed
376 a significant relationship with one of the objective variables. This was the perception of
377 how noisy the street is (i) for the case of air pressure (AP), which explained 14% of the
378 variation, while for luminosity it was the perception of how noisy the city is (h), with a
379 27% explanation of its variation. If these results are compared with those of previous
380 studies analysing the relationship between meteorological variables and noise annoyance
381 from different sound sources, they are satisfactory. For example, Miedema et al.
382 (Miedema et al., 2005) found a R^2 less than 0.19 but for multivariate models that did not
383 only include meteorological variables. L_{den} (dB), aircraft and railway variables were also
384 considered in the multivariate models. Only sound indicators show a high correlation with
385 noise effects as shown in Table 2.

386 Regarding the variable of temperature (T), the values of the slope coefficient with respect
387 to almost all of the correlated subjective variables were similar and had a negative sign,
388 indicating that the values given by the respondents for the subjective variables decrease
389 as the temperature increases. In contrast, a positive value was obtained for the subjective
390 variable of perception of how noisy the city is (h). In the case of the significant
391 relationship between air pressure (AP) and the perception of how noisy the street is (i),
392 the slope coefficient was negative, meaning that the rating of this variable decreases as
393 air pressure increases. However, for the relationship between luminosity (logLU) and the
394 perception of how noisy the city is (i), this coefficient had a positive value. Hence, of the
395 environmental variables considered, temperature showed the highest number of
396 significant relationships with the different effects of noise and the perception of how noisy
397 is the environment. The negative slope suggests that people may perceive the effects of
398 noise as being of lower intensity in environments with softer temperatures.

399 Another aspect of interest in Table 4 is the analysis of the values of intercept coefficients.
 400 For the significant relationships of temperature and luminosity with the subjective
 401 variables, all values were positive and within the interval of the 0–10 rating scale used in
 402 the surveys. This gives an idea of the base value when temperature and luminosity tend
 403 to zero.

404 The values of the subjective variables resulting from applying these equations remained
 405 within the scale of 0–10 for ranges of approximately -9–25°C for temperature, 983–1025
 406 hPa for air pressure and 0–105 klux for luminosity. These ranges of environmental
 407 variables are wide and include a great range of environmental conditions in which these
 408 regression models could be considered valid.

409 3.2.3. Acoustic variables

410 The values for the different parameters of the regression analysis between the subjective
 411 dependent variables and the acoustic independent variables that showed significant
 412 correlation in Table 2 are presented in Table 5. For each of these five variables, that is the
 413 A-weighted equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}), maximum sound level (L_{AFmax}) and percentile
 414 levels (L_{10} , L_{50} and L_{90}), the values of the slope, intercept, determination coefficient (R^2)
 415 and significance level are given. For the streets studied, these independent variables took
 416 values in the range 48–73 dBA for L_{Aeq} , 70–89 dBA for L_{AFmax} , 47–77 dBA for L_{10} , 40–
 417 70 dBA for L_{50} and 37–60 dBA for L_{90} as shown in Table 1.

418 Table 5. Regression parameters among all subjective variables and the objective acoustic
 419 variables L_{Aeq} , L_{AFmax} , L_{10} , L_{50} and L_{90} .

		Subjective variables								
		a)	b)	c)	d)	e)	f)	g)	h)	i)
L_{Aeq}	Slope	0.24	0.18	0.15	0.21	0.25	0.18	0.24	-0.08	0.20
	Intercept	-11.49	-8.24	-6.49	-10.61	-12.63	-8.43	-12.20	10.42	-7.54

	R²	0.47***	0.37***	0.21*	0.39***	0.42***	0.29**	0.41***	0.15*	0.40***
<i>L_{AFmax}</i>	Slope	0.22	0.14	--	0.16	0.21	--	0.17	-0.11	0.16
	Intercept	-14.17	-7.98	--	-10.65	-14.16	--	-11.23	14.54	-8.17
	R²	0.32**	0.17*	--	0.19*	0.25**	--	0.17*	0.25**	0.22*
<i>L_{AF10}</i>	Slope	0.20	0.16	0.13	0.17	0.20	0.14	0.19	-0.06	0.16
	Intercept	-9.60	-7.34	-5.59	-8.50	-10.21	-6.81	-9.78	9.62	-5.82
	R²	0.50***	0.44***	0.24**	0.39***	0.42***	0.29**	0.40***	0.14*	0.42***
<i>L_{AF50}</i>	Slope	0.20	0.17	0.16	0.18	0.22	0.16	0.21	-0.06	0.17
	Intercept	-7.81	-6.29	-5.82	-7.55	-9.38	-6.37	-9.12	9.08	-4.68
	R²	0.50***	0.47***	0.34***	0.43***	0.49***	0.36***	0.48***	0.15*	0.44***
<i>L_{AF90}</i>	Slope	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.20	0.24	0.18	0.23	--	0.19
	Intercept	-7.53	-7.31	-7.67	-7.59	-9.17	-6.65	-8.67	--	-5.03
	R²	0.41***	0.50***	0.43***	0.37***	0.41***	0.33**	0.38***	--	0.41***

420 -- Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).

421 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

422 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

423 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

424 Most of the relationships between the subjective variables related to the effects of noise
425 on people and the acoustic variables are significant (Table 4). These relationships have a
426 higher level of significance in the case of L_{Aeq} , L_{10} , L_{50} and L_{90} , which can explain up to
427 50% of the variation in some variables such as a) and b). The variation had a value of
428 between 47% and 29% for the other effects of noise on the population, such as c), d), e),
429 f), g), i). In the case of the acoustic variable L_{AFmax} , the results for the significant
430 correlation explain variations in the subjective variables of between 32% and 17%. The
431 explanations of the variability of the studied variables related to the effects of noise reach
432 high values in the case of some acoustic variables taking into account that they are
433 subjective variables. The L_{Aeq} is the indicator most commonly used in previous studies to
434 study its relationship with noise annoyance. A Spearman's rho less than 0.24 was found
435 in the correlation between noise annoyance and L_{den} by Dzhambov et al. (Dzhambov et
436 al., 2017) and Felcyn et al. (Felcyn et al., 2018). A similar value of Pearson's correlation
437 coefficient ($r = 0.26 - 0.30$) was also found by Paviotti et al. (Paviotti and Vogiatzis,
438 2012) and Tao et al. (Tao et al., 2020). Therefore, the explanation of variability does not

439 exceed 9% in these previous bivariate analyses. In multivariate studies using different
440 sound indicators or combinations of them, R^2 values similar to those in this study are
441 achieved (Nguyen et al., 2012) (Lee et al., 2021).

442 It is interesting to see how the capacity of the sound indices analysed here to explain the
443 annoyance in the ears (c) increases as the value becomes more representative of the
444 background noise level at the site. The L_{AFmax} index is not significant and L_{Aeq} is
445 significant at 95%, while L_{AF50} and L_{AF90} are significant at 99.9%. The last of these
446 explains the highest variability (43%). The statistical sound variables are therefore better
447 than the energetic sound variables in this respect, in relation to the variable c). Note that
448 the case of the variable b) is similar in terms of the explained variability, while the
449 variable a) does not follow the same pattern. In the cases of the variables d), e), f), g), and
450 i), the index L_{AF50} seems to be the best predictor of their variability, which is an indicator
451 of average values over time. Finally, it is also interesting to note that that the capacity of
452 the sound indices analysed to explain the variability of the perception of how noisy is the
453 city (h) is low or not significant in all cases. It can be observed that L_{AF90} is not significant,
454 while L_{AFmax} is significant at 99%, the only variable for which this is seen.

455 Another noteworthy point in relation to Table 5 is that for each acoustic variable, the
456 slope of the linear regression equation is positive for all issues related to the effects of
457 noise or the perception of the studied environment; that is, the value indicated by the
458 respondents for the subjective variables increases as the sound indicators take on a higher
459 value. However, this is not the case for the subjective variable perception of how noisy
460 the city is (h), where the negative value of the slope reflects an inversely proportional
461 linear relationship. The value of the subjective variables resulting from applying these
462 equations remains within the scale 0–10 for a range of sound levels of approximately 51–
463 87 dBA for L_{Aeq} , 68–101 dBA for L_{AFmax} , 52–98 dBA for L_{10} , 44–86 dBA for L_{50} and 39–

464 79 dBA for L_{90} . These ranges for the acoustic variables, over which the subjective
465 variables remain within the scale used in the survey, cover a wide range of urban
466 environments in which road traffic is the predominant source of noise, meaning that the
467 linear equations obtained in this study relating the subjective variables to the acoustic
468 variables could be considered valid for many other cities of different sizes.

469 **3.3 Multivariate regression analysis**

470 In addition to the bivariate regression analysis presented in the previous sections for each
471 group of objective variables, a multivariate analysis was also carried out using stepwise
472 regression. The street category (SC) was recoded as a dummy variable in order to include
473 it as an independent variable in the regression analysis. Consequently, the five different
474 street categories were grouped into main streets (Categories 1 to 3) and neighbourhood
475 streets (Categories 4 and 5). Neighbourhood streets were considered as the reference level
476 (value = 0) for this binary variable (SC_b).

477 Since Table 1 revealed that the acoustic variables are those that individually explained a
478 higher percentage of the variability of the subjective variables related to the effects of
479 environmental noise and the perception of noisy urban spaces, a stepwise regression was
480 first proposed in this section considering only the urban and environmental variables. The
481 aim was to study the extent to which combinations of these objective variables would
482 allow for a prediction of the effects of environmental noise and its perception in urban
483 environments with no need for *in situ* acoustic measurements and, therefore, reducing the
484 production costs of carrying out this type of research associated with acoustic
485 measurement equipment. Table 6 shows the results from the stepwise regression between
486 the subjective variables and the urban and environmental variables, where B is the

487 regression coefficient and R^2 (coefficient of determination) shows the percentage of
 488 explanation of the variability of the subjective variable.

489 Table 6. Regression parameters among the subjective variables and the urban and
 490 environmental variables.

Subjective variables	Objective variables	Constant	<i>B</i>	R^2
a)	SC _b	3.05	1.82	0.18
b)	SC _b	2.74	1.68	0.20
c)	H	0.92	0.13	0.20
d)	SC _b	1.85	2.29	0.30
e)	SC _b	8.83	2.82	0.63
	T		-0.31	
f)	H	1.87	-0.13	0.25
	SC _b		1.98	
g)	SC _b	1.85	3.08	0.44
h)	logLU	4.31	1.58	0.27
i)	SC _b	6.28	-2.08	0.29

491 Although all urban and environmental variables were initially considered in the
 492 multivariate regression analysis, the resulting models have only one independent variable
 493 in most cases (see Table 6). In this regard, bivariate models obtained from a stepwise
 494 regression, based essentially on urban variables, provide explanations of between 18%
 495 and 44% for the variability in the effects and the perception of environmental noise. This
 496 explanation of variability is similar to that provided by sound indicators for some effects
 497 (c: annoyance ears, and f: interrupting phone). It is also interesting to note the effect of
 498 the street category on the prediction of most of the subjective variables, which suggests
 499 that this categorisation method could also be useful for predicting the effects of
 500 environmental noise on people and their perceptions of noise in urban spaces.

501 Table 6 also reveals that in the case of the subjective variable raising the volume of the
 502 voice (e), models based on a combination of urban and environmental objective variables

503 allow for a high explanation of its variability. For this noise effect, a model containing
504 only the urban variable SC_b explains 45% of its variation. When combined in a
505 multivariate model with an environmental variable such as temperature (T), a significant
506 increase in explanation of up to 54% is found. Moreover, when the urban variable of
507 average building height (H) is included, the explanation of the variability of raising
508 volume (e) reaches a value of 63%. This percentage of variability is much higher than
509 that found for any of the sound indicators shown in Table 5. Hence, reliable predictions
510 for some variables related to the effects of environmental noise in urban environments
511 can be obtained from a combination of urban and environmental variables, and this offers
512 a possible alternative to models based on acoustic variables. In this context, the urban
513 variable related to street geometry, i.e. the average building height (H), also showed a
514 relationship with the perception of the sound environment (Prida et al., 2019).

515 After the analysis considering only the urban and environmental objective variables, a
516 new multivariate regression analysis between the subjective variables and all the
517 objective variables (urban, environmental and acoustic variables) was carried out. The
518 hypothesis was to analyse whether the use of both urban and environmental variables
519 could complement the predictions made by acoustic variables with respect to the effects
520 and perceptions of noise. Thus, in addition to looking for possible alternative models
521 containing only urban-environmental variables, the aim was also to develop models that
522 complement the predictions made by the acoustic variables. The results presented in Table
523 7 show that for the variables: raising volume (e), interrupting phone (f), raising phone (g)
524 and noisy city (h), the inclusion of urban and environmental variables improves the
525 prediction. In these models, the acoustic index L_{AF50} provides an explanation of variability
526 of 49% for raising volume (e), 36% for interrupting phone, and 48% for raising phone (g)
527 (see Table 5), which increases to 59%, 48%, and 65%, respectively, with the variables

528 SC_b, logLU, and H. For the perception of how noisy is the city (h), a model is obtained in
 529 which the acoustic index L_{AFmax} explains 25% of its variability (see Table 5), reaching a
 530 value of 41% with the environmental variable luminosity (logLU). The percentage
 531 explanations for the variability of the different effects and perceptions of noise are high
 532 compared to results obtained in recent studies (Chung et al., 2022) (Lee et al., 2021)
 533 (Preisendörfer et al., 2022) (Tangermann et al., 2022). Chung et al. (Chung et al., 2022)
 534 consider that a Pearson's r of 0.60 is strong in view of the subjectivity of the variables
 535 analysed. Furthermore, these multivariate models have a high efficiency given the low
 536 number of independent variables. Lee et al. (Lee et al., 2021) use 12 independent variables
 537 to achieve a 60% explanation of the variability of noise annoyance.

538 Table 7. Multivariate regression parameters between subjective variables and urban,
 539 environmental and acoustic variables.

Subjective variables	Objective variables	Constant	B	R^2
e)	L_{AF50}	-5.88	0.15	0.59
	SC _b		1.88	
f)	L_{AF50}	-9.71	0.19	0.48
	logLU		1.81	
g)	L_{AF50}	-6.11	0.17	0.65
	SC _b		1.82	
	H		-0.09	
h)	L_{AFmax}	11.63	-0.09	0.41
	logLU		1.28	

540 4. CONCLUSIONS

541 An analysis performed of the relationships between the responses of surveyed pedestrians
 542 in urban environments about some specific effects of noise and their perceptions of noisy
 543 environments with those values registered for urban, environmental and acoustic
 544 variables led to the following conclusions.

545 Concerning the urban variables, an increase in the average height of the buildings
546 increases some related perceived noise effects. In fact, a significant positive correlation
547 was found for the subjective variables irritability (a), startle (b), annoyance in the ears (c)
548 and perception of how noisy the street is (i) with the average height of the buildings on
549 the street, with explanations of the variability ranging from 14% to 20%. When the
550 environmental variables were taken into account, a significant negative correlation was
551 found only between temperature (T) and several variables related to the effects of noise
552 and the perception of noisy environments. This finding suggests that the values assigned
553 by the respondents for these variables tended to decrease as the temperature increased.
554 This study makes an initial approach to the analysis of the possible effects that urban and
555 environmental variables have on the annoyance or effects of noise, and presents a
556 methodology that can be applied in other urban environments with different
557 characteristics and conditions. The considered ranges of environmental variables allow to
558 cover a great range of environmental conditions, but it would also be interesting to extend
559 this research to cities in which streets have a wider range of average building heights.

560 The explanations of the variability in the subjective variables related to the perception of
561 the effects of noise reach noteworthy values in the case of some acoustic variables. The
562 indicators L_{Aeq} , L_{10} , L_{50} and L_{90} explained up to 50% of the variation of irritability (a) and
563 startle (b) and values of between 29% and 47% were found for other effects of noise on
564 the population and the perception of noisy environments. It is also interesting to highlight
565 the capacity of some sound indices such as L_{AF50} and L_{AF90} to explain the variable ear
566 annoyance (c), which increases as the index becomes more representative of the
567 background noise level at the site and reaches an explanation of variability of 43% in the
568 case of L_{AF90} . For the variables interrupting a conversation with someone nearby (d),
569 raising the volume of the voice to talk with someone nearby (e), interrupting a phone

570 conversation (f), raising the volume of the voice on a phone conversation (g) and
571 perception of how noisy is the street (i), the index L_{AF50} was the better predictor of their
572 variability. In the case of the perception of how noisy is the city (h), L_{AFmax} was the only
573 variable that showed a significant correlation at 99%.

574 A stepwise regression analysis showed that if only urban and environmental variables are
575 considered, models with a single urban or environmental variable provide explanations
576 of between 18% and 44% of the effects and perception of environmental noise.
577 Furthermore, the efficient combination of these urban and environmental variables in
578 multivariate models can lead to an increase in the explanation of subjective variables
579 provided by acoustic variables. In this vein, increases in the explanation of the variability
580 of between 10% and 17% were found for some subjective variables. In the case of the
581 subjective variable raising volume (e), a model based on the combination of variables as
582 SC_b , average building height (H) and temperature (T) was able to provide explanations
583 of up to 63% of its variability. The variable SC_b again provided an increase of about 10%
584 in the explanation of the subjective variables in these models. Therefore, the results
585 suggest that the categorisation method, in addition to being useful in stratifying road
586 traffic noise in cities, could also be valuable in terms of predicting the effects of
587 environmental noise on people and their perception of noise in urban spaces.

588 The specific analysis of each urban and environmental variable recorded in this study has
589 shown those that have a significant relationship with the specific effects of noise and
590 therefore those that can be used as an alternative or complement in future prediction
591 models of noise effects.

592 The number of respondents in this study implies a limitation, as the sample size of 105
593 individuals, being an adequate number to be representative of the population studied, is

594 at the lower limit. In addition, the presence of the same or similar values for the objective
595 variables recorded in the different surveys carried out at each sampling point precluded
596 the use of bivariate and multivariate linear regression analysis by surveys as they did not
597 meet the assumptions of normality, homoscedasticity and randomness. For this reason,
598 the study was limited to studying the mean values obtained at each sampling point which,
599 due to the also low and constant variability of the subjective variables at each sampling
600 point, the results obtained by points were similar to those obtained by surveys. The
601 variability of the objective and subjective variables was mainly due to their different
602 locations and, therefore, using a survey analysis would bias the results of the overall
603 perception of the city because the same number of surveys were not carried out at each
604 point. Despite limitations in the sample size (105) due to the emergence of the pandemic
605 and in an analysis based on values by location (29), the careful methodology and,
606 fundamentally, the novel design of the questions asked in the survey can serve as a guide
607 for future studies to validate the results obtained in this study.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Author contributions statement

David Montes González: Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Guillermo Rey-Gozalo:** Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Funding acquisition.